

THE CREATION SALE AND THE PURCHASE OF INNOVATIONS UNDER THE CONDITION OF MARKET ECONOMY

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Annotation: The development of technology, capability of innovation and efficacious innovative policy play a crucial role in the motivation of innovations in the market economy. Motivation is something that stimulates the active activity of certain needs and their collection of motives in a specific field. The motivation of innovations is the innovative activity of the activity of the producer and the manager and broadly, it is the process of technology and the sales of innovations at the same time purchase plus the urge of them to be used actively in the field of economy.

Keywords: importance, innovations, process, producer, Purpose, Motives, Causes,

Specific, product, to benefit, environment, enterprise and Increasing, modernized, the investment opportunity.

In order to know the importance of innovations in the economy, firstly, it is important to create an effective competitiveness. One of the main factors in developing innovative economy in Uzbekistan is undoubtedly, human capital and the way it should be developed according to the modern standards. This human capital namely intellect should be alert and be eager in understanding new technologies and mainly, learnt the basics of this subject skillfully and should be able to experiment them in real life. From the appearance of the innovations it is clear to find out that a lot of patience and determination give a sign that has been done over a long time. But in most cases, the process of the innovations being confessed and absorbed by the society is more difficult rather than creating them. As our first president said that: In order to provide the competitiveness of a product, firstly, searching for big and fairly normal projects related to technology field is needed and in order to be able to do this, the boss and engineer of every company needs to know their responsibility so that they can find the resources and financial aid which is in need. In this field, having strict control and creating the transfer of innovations in the industrial enterprise

give a rise to a number of problems. The development of technology, capability of innovation and efficacious innovative policy play a crucial role in the motivation of innovations in the market economy. Motivation is something that stimulates the active activity of certain needs and their collection of motives in a specific field. The motivation of innovations is the innovative activity of the activity of the producer and the manager and broadly, it is the process of technology and the sales of innovations at the same time purchase plus the urge of them to be used actively in the field of economy.

It is necessary to look through the motivation of innovations in two ways:

The creations and the sale motivations of innovations

The purchase of the motivations of the innovations

All motivations consist of these 4 parts:

Purpose

Motives

Causes

Eagerness to achieve the goal

The purpose of the creation of the motivations and of the purchase of the motivations is to help the producer of a specific product to benefit from the business which he runs and as well as, the funding of the benefit which was gained into some other enterprises, raising the quality of the product in the market combined with increasing the competitiveness in the market. Motives are needed according to the special need of a producer who is running a business.

The creation and the sale of innovations are based on several factors:

Increase in the level of competitiveness

Changes in the regulative production of products

The development of technologies

The changes in the field of tax

Achievements in the world market

Competitive market remains the the unseparable part of all conditions which may happen. The increasing level of competitiveness urges enterprises to be leading and stimulates them to find ways to invade markets. Regulative production and sale process is the effective process in which the working process of a company is controlled according to market rules and the strict that were announced by responsible institutions. Production is based on putting the sale process in the order and have to use different type and special mechanisms widely. Achievements in the market of the world are considered to be one of the

factors in the creation of innovations. In the developing period, investors have more free capital and this process enables producer to offer their own product and the tactics he is going to use to run the upcoming business.

These are the motives in the sales of innovations:

The competitiveness of the owner of the enterprise and Increasing the rank
Benefiting from the capital in the long run which has been put today

Main objective factors are the following:

Changes in the regulative production-sale process

Changes in the field of taxes

Achievements in the world market

It is clear from above that these factors are suitable with the factors in the saling motivation factors. However, in this case under the activity of an enterprise lies client's needs and benefits.

Our president SH.M.Mirziyoyev said that it is our crucial duty to create the environment of innovation in the outlook of our nation. Unless, there is innovation, there will not be any competitiveness, progress in in any field. If we do not advocate changes in this field, we cannot be in one step together with the tempo and the awesome success of the technology field. In 2017-2021 years Actions Strategy was made based on 5 fields that are the main things in developing economy, toughening the stableness of macro economy and keeping the economic growth at a high level, plus increasing the level of the national economy, making the conditions of the rural economy be modernized, protecting the right of the private property and making the investment opportunity in our country to attract foreign investors to make an investment. These all activities are intended to develop our country.

The following priorities are made in this field:

The increasing of the openness and competitiveness of the economy

Developing industrial independence

Toughening stableness of macroeconomy

Modernizing and diversifying leading producers' branch

Refining the the finance bank field

Enlargening the contact in economy with foreign countries

Attracting foreign investment

